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**TAXONOMIC COMPOSITION AND DIRECTIONS OF USE OF THE GENUS
SENECIUS (*SENECIO* L.) DISTRIBUTED IN THE NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS
REPUBLIC**

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Abstract. *The presented article provides information on the taxonomic spectrum and directions of use of the species included in the genus *Senecio* L. of the family *Lamiaceae* Martinov, nom, cons. distributed in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. It was found from the conducted studies that 10 species of this genus are found in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. According to the literature data and our studies, the species belonging to the genus are used in economic, ecological, decorative and medical fields.*

Keywords: *Senecio L.1, genus 2, food source 3, decorative 4, endemic 5.*

Аннотация. *В представленной статье рассматриваются представители семейства *Lamiaceae* Martinov, nom, cons., распространенные во флоре Нахчыванской Автономной Республики. Приведена информация о таксономическом спектре и использовании видов, относящихся к роду *Сенецио* (*Senecio* L.) семейства *Сенецио*. Исследования показали, что во флоре Нахчыванской Автономной Республики встречается 10 видов этого рода. Согласно литературным данным и нашим исследованиям, виды, входящие в род, используются в хозяйственной, экологической, декоративной и медицинской сферах.*

Introduction

The flora of Nakhchivan is very rich and diverse, which is due to its diverse climatic and geographical conditions. The flora of Nakhchivan includes numerous species, both endemic and common in the flora of Azerbaijan in general. One of the widespread families in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is the *Asteraceae*. The distribution of the *Asteraceae* family in Nakhchivan occupies an important place in the flora of this region. In semi-arid areas and mountainous regions, these plants efficiently use water resources. The warm summers and cold winters of Nakhchivan determine the life cycle of these plants. Plants belonging to the family are distributed in various ecosystems in the nature of Nakhchivan, increasing the richness of the local flora. At the same time, these plants also play an important role in the local economy, especially as agricultural and medicinal plants. *Asteraceae* also remain one of the main elements of the nature of Nakhchivan, maintaining the balance of ecology. The family is represented by 92 genera and 357 species. There are 19 species of the genus in Azerbaijan, 12 species in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Material and methodology of the study

The studies were conducted in various areas of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in 2023-2024. The object of the study was rocky and roadside areas of the region, and the species of the genus *Senecio* L. were taken as the material. The definition and clarification of the names of the species belonging to the genus *Senecio* L. Flora of Azerbaijan [14] and other works. The latest taxonomic changes were clarified with World Flora Online [33].

Discussion and conclusions of the study

In the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the genus *Senecio* is one of the important plant species included in the rich flora of the region. There are 19 species of the genus in Azerbaijan, and

12 species in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The systematic composition, ecological groups, areal class, altitudinal zone, flowering and fruiting phase of the species included in the genus are listed in the table below (Table 1.).

Table 1.

S/№	Species name	Ecological groups	Altitudinal zone	Areal class	Flowering and fruiting phase
1.	<i>Senecio thyrsophorus</i> C.Koch	Mesophyte	Mid-mountain and subalpine belt	Unknown	VI,VII-VII,VIII
2.	<i>Senecio grandidentatus</i> Ledeb	Mesophyte	Central highland belt	Atropaten	VI,VIII-VII,IX
3.	<i>Senecio lipskyi</i> Lomak	Xerophyte	Mid-mountain and subalpine belt	Atropaten	VI,VIII-VIII
4.	<i>Senecio othonnae</i> Bieb	Mesophyte	Mid-mountain and subalpine belt	Atropaten	VII,VIII-VIII,IX
5.	<i>Senecio erucifolius</i> L	Mesophyte	Central highland belt	Unknown	VII-VIII
6.	<i>Senecio racemosus</i> (Bieb.) DC	Mesophyte	Mid-mountain and subalpine belt	Atropaten	VI,VII-VII,VIII
7.	<i>Senecio taraxacifolius</i> (Bieb.) DC	Mesoxerophyte	In rocky and mountainous areas	Caucasus	VII-IX
8.	<i>Senecio vernalis</i> Waldst. & Kit	Mesoxerophyte	Central highland belt	Europe	IV,VII-V,IX
9.	<i>Senecio paucifolius</i> DC	Mesoxerophyte	In rocky and mountainous areas	Atropaten	VII-VIII
10.	<i>Senecio orientalis</i> Willd	Mesophyte	Mid-mountain and subalpine belt	Atropaten	VI,VII-VII,VIII

Taxonomic composition of species belonging to the genus *Senecio* L.

During the analysis of the ecological groups of the species specific to the genus, it was determined that 1 species out of 10 species belongs to the xerophyte ecological group, 6 species to the mesophyte ecological group, and 3 species to the mesoxerophyte ecological group.

Ecological groups of the genus *Senecio* L.

Based on the collected literature data and personal field research, it was determined that the species of the genus belong to different areal classes, which allows us to determine the migration routes of the species to the area. Based on zonal and regional principles, it was found that the species included in the genus are grouped into 3 areal classes. As noted in the table, Atropatan is represented by 6, and the Caucasus and Europe areal classes are represented by 1 species each. The areal class of the other 2 species is unknown.

The areal class of the genus *Senecio* L.

Some species of the genus *Senecio* L. are toxic. Therefore, caution is advised when handling or handling these plants. Species of the genus *Senecio* are grown for ornamental purposes in horticulture. Some *Senecio* species are used in folk medicine for their anti-inflammatory, wound healing and spasmolytic properties. In addition, the plant also plays an important role in preventing soil erosion, as it grows on rocky and dry soils.

Senecio erucifolius is used in traditional medicine to treat various diseases. The plant is reported to have diuretic, anti-inflammatory and antirheumatic properties.

Figure 1. *Senecio erucifolius*

Senecio grandidentatus is an important part of local ecosystems in preventing soil erosion and as a food source for some insect species.

Senecio lipskyi is used in folk medicine as an anti-inflammatory, analgesic and wound healing agent. These plants reduce soil erosion in mountainous and rocky areas and serve as a food source for pollinators such as bees and butterflies.

Senecio thyrsophorus contains toxic substances such as pyrrolizidine alkaloids, which are harmful to the liver. Therefore, it is important to be careful and seek expert advice when using plants of this genus for medicinal purposes.

Senecio taraxacifolius is used to prevent erosion – to strengthen the soil. It is not recommended to take it internally and expert advice should be sought before using it. It is dangerous for pregnant women and children.

Senecio othonnae species is a food source for bees and other pollinating insects. Thus, the plant plays an important role as part of the ecosystem. It is used in gardening due to its decorative properties.

Information on the use of *Senecio paucifolius* species is very limited. The plant has anti-inflammatory, analgesic and wound healing properties. However, since plants of this genus may contain pyrrolizidine alkaloids, internal use is harmful and is toxic to the liver. Therefore, caution should be taken in the medical use of *Senecio paucifolius* species.

Senecio vernalis is used in traditional medicine to accelerate wound healing by having an anti-inflammatory effect, to treat stomach problems by affecting the digestive system, and to treat respiratory diseases by having an expectorant and anti-cough effect.

Figure 2. *Senecio vernalis*

Senecio orientalis species, because they are flowering, serve as a food source for bees, butterflies and other pollinating insects. Thus, they play an important role in the ecosystem.

Senecio recemosus species has anti-inflammatory effects, wound healing and reducing inflammation, analgesic effects and reducing headaches and joint pain in traditional medicine, and antimicrobial properties, antibacterial and antifungal effects.

Numerous species of the *Asteraceae* family are widespread in the mountainous and semi-arid areas of Nakhchivan. These plants are usually found in plateaus, meadows, pastures, forest edges and even mountain slopes. In Nakhchivan, numerous species of *Asteraceae*, especially blooming in the summer months, add beauty to local ecosystems and provide environmental diversity. *Asteraceae* are widely distributed in various areas - from the tropics to cold regions. The most common species are found in grassy and alpine meadows, even in urban areas. Numerous species of these plants are cultivated by humans for various purposes and collected in large quantities. The *Asteraceae* family helps to understand the role of plants in the ecosystem and their importance in human life. This family occupies a unique place in the world flora in terms of both natural beauty and economic importance. The complex structure of their flowers and fruits makes these plants very interesting both biologically and aesthetically. The *Asteraceae* family is widespread in the nature of Nakhchivan with its various species and occupies an important place in the flora of this region. The climate, soils and various ecosystems of Nakhchivan create favorable conditions for the development of *Asteraceae*. Plants belonging to this family grow easily in both freshwater ecosystems and dry and semi-arid areas.

The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, which is mentioned as the research zone, is a favorable area for xerophytic plants in terms of climate and geographical conditions. The xerophytic ecological plant group includes drought-tolerant plants, and these plants are adapted to the dry climate. They use water effectively through a number of adaptations. The role of xerophytes in ecosystems is very large, because they protect the soil, provide food and shelter for animals, and also support the sustainability of the natural environment. With their ecological and economic importance, xerophytes provide significant benefits to both nature and humans [13, 22, 23, 24, 28].

Regardless of the studied area, herbaceous plants in all areas are closely related to species of a number of families and form various groupings [9, 10, 11, 15, 25, 26, 27, 31, 32, 34, 35].

In Nakhchivan, xerophytic herbaceous plants are a field related to the cultivation of plants that require little water and are drought-resistant, taking into account the arid climate and soil conditions

of the region. Xerophytic plants grow in accordance with the local flora in the semi-desert and steppe zones of Nakhchivan and these plants can be used in both agriculture and livestock. Xerophytic herbaceous plants have great potential for local agriculture and farming by ensuring the efficient use of soil and water resources [1, 2, 8, 10, 20, 21, 22, 29, 30]. Along with herbaceous plants, forest and shrub plants are widely distributed, creating various complex ecosystems. These ecosystems play a key role in maintaining ecological balance by providing significant support to local flora and fauna.

Thus, in the resulting phytocenoses, plants belonging to the *Fabaceae*, *Malvaceae*, *Rosaceae* and many other families act as dominant species [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 12, 16, 17, 18, 19].

Thus, the above-mentioned does not fully reflect the directions of use of species belonging to the genus *Senecio* L. It is considered appropriate to study all the characteristics of the studied genus in a comprehensive manner in our future studies.

Conclusion

1. During the conducted research, it was concluded that 10 species of the genus *Senecio* L. are found in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. It was found that all species belonging to the genus are decorative, medical and ecological in nature.

2. During the analysis of the ecological groups of the species included in the genus, it was found that 1 species of the genus is xerophytic, 6 species are mesophytic, and 3 species are mesoxerophytic.

3. According to the analysis of the geographical areal classes, 6 species of the genus are Atropatan, 1 species is Caucasian, 1 species is European, and the other 2 species are unknown.

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